

WAST3G: A Comprehensive WCDMA Simulation Tool for Third-Generation Mobile Communications

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we describe a software tool (*Wideband CDMA Simulation Tool for Third Generation Mobile Communications*, WAST3G) that simulates a mobile communication system based on UMTS. It can be used as a test-bed for new algorithms and methods for deconvolution, demodulation, despreading, equalization and detection, aiming on 3G systems performance and technics. It can also be used as a learning tool for the operation of wireless communications systems in general, and 3G systems in particular, because it implements all necessary steps for a mobile station that was “turned off” to achieve communication, including synchronization and system registration procedures. All these features make WAST3G a very powerful tool for academic and industrial purposes.

1 Introduction

The evolution of mobile communications systems towards third generation (3G) has been based on several proposals of Radio Transmission Technologies (RTT). In Europe, a strong candidate to standardize 3G systems has been submitted by ETSI and is known as the UMTS Terrestrial Radio Access (UTRA) RTT proposal[1]. Given its importance, a good understanding of this RTT-proposal capabilities, shortcomings, and implementation issues are of paramount importance for engineers and researchers involved in the development and analysis of any constituent part of the system. Furthermore, as more undergraduate and graduate students as well as engineers become interested in the field, a comprehensive software tool which can be used for teaching and research simulations can be useful for academics and industrial purposes.

Communication-system softwares designed to test algorithms or channel models usually do a good job in simulating transmitted and received signals corresponding to voice or data coded symbols. They usually focus on a specific task and, for all the obvious reasons, do not implement all steps and channels required to establish a connection or to control the operation of the communicating parties. On the other hand, standards, books,

and radio-interface proposals do a great job in describing channels individually and how they are to be constructed. The amount of details in this case is restricted to “how the signals should look like,” not on the specific details of implementation. Details are left to the system-implementation engineers and, in general, become proprietary information. For these reasons, many gaps are left between theory and practice in training courses at undergraduate and graduate levels.

As part of a larger project that encompass research, development, and teaching at graduate and undergraduate levels in the Signal Processing Laboratory at the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, a simulation tool using MATLAB[®] was developed for 3G mobile communications. It is not only a test-bed for the implementation and joint operation of all subsystems that are part of a wireless-communication prototype for connecting two computers in a base station-mobile station arrangement. It also serves as a stimulating learning tool, as an aid to teach the operation of wireless communications systems in general and 3G systems in particular, and as a simulator for testing new algorithms and methods for deconvolution, demodulation, despreading, equalization, and detection. Furthermore, the tool is flexible for the introduction of new receiver structures or for the modification of the existing ones. This is a feature that is particularly appealing if it is to be used as a research tool.

The system simulates a communication between two mobile stations that are geographically located at the same cell. The communication is established through a base station. The mobile stations connect to a base station and one mobile station can start the communication with the other following all the procedures described by the UTRA specification. The user can set and try different parameters for the system with complete control and full access to the connection status.

2 The WAST3 Software

2.1 User interface

The main screen has the controls to provide a simple interaction with the simulator. The user can change

the configuration of the base station, altering parameters like the spreading factors of the control channels and the maximum allowed spreading factor for the dedicated channels in the cell. The user can control two mobile stations connected to the system and change their configuration using the correspondent *Options* button. Snapshots of the main screen and of the options screen are shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2.

Figure 1: WAST3G main screen.

Figure 2: WAST3G base station options screen.

As the simulation takes place, messages corresponding to the current tasks being executed are shown in the status window in the bottom of the main screen. The *Report* button shows a report of the system operation, which can be saved to a file. Information about the status of the two mobile stations controlled by the user is available within the colored indicators that show if the mobile station is on, synchronized to the base station,

registered to the system and if it is connected to another mobile station.

The menus *File I/O* and *Options* give access to general configurations, like the files that will be used for data transmission and the parameters for the channel model. The menu *Simulation* gives the user the possibility to bypass all the synchronization and system registration steps and start the data connection between the two mobile stations.

2.2 Physical Layer

The physical layer performs the transmission of the information over the radio interface. All the transport channels described in the UTRA proposal have been implemented, and the choice for the appropriate channel to use depends on the type of the information, as will be described in the sequence. For the downlink, separation of channels is accomplished by the orthogonal codes used for spreading, and for the uplink, separation is accomplished by the spreading codes and the scrambling codes used by each mobile station. There is also the Synchronization Channel (SCH), that is not considered a transport channel, because there is no data being transmitted, but only symbols that are used for synchronization purposes.

A convolutional encoder with $K = 9$ and $r = 1/3$ and a Viterbi decoder are used for all transport channels, except for the RACH, where error control is done by CRC check.

The channels are modulated in a one-sample-per-chip basis, summed, and filtered through a multipath channel model, whose parameters are determined by the user. The receiver is implemented as a RAKE receiver that has assumed knowledge of the channel coefficients.

Here follows a brief description of the transport channels and the related protocols. We developed all the described protocols, since they were not specified in the UTRA proposal.

2.2.1 Broadcast Channel (BCH)

The BCH is a common control channel (downlink) always transmitted with information about other channels and about the cell. The following information is transmitted on the BCH:

- spreading factor (SF) of the Forward Access Channel (FACH);
- SF of the Paging Channel (PCH);
- number of the Gold code of the preamble part of the Random Access Burst.
- minimum available SF for the Dedicated Channel (DCH);
- transmitted power of BCH, FACH and PCH (same power for all);
- Signal to Interference Ratio (SIR);

- uplink interference.

Although power control is not implemented in the simulator, all the protocols were developed so that it can be implemented on future versions of the software.

2.2.2 Forward Access Channel (FACH)

The FACH is a common control channel (downlink) transmitted only when there's a message to a mobile station and the system knows the location cell of the mobile station. The FACH carries the following messages:

- Mobile station registered: mobile station registration confirmation.
- Invalid subscriber: mobile station tries to register in the system but it's not a valid subscriber.
- Communication established: communication establishment confirmation.

2.2.3 Paging Channel (PCH)

The PCH is a common control channel (downlink) transmitted only when there's a message to a mobile station and the system does not know the location cell of the mobile station. Typically used for *paging* messages.

2.2.4 Random Access Channel (RACH)

Common channel (uplink) used to carry control information from a mobile station. Always sent in bursts. Four types of bursts are allowed:

- Voice channel request: requests a dedicated channel to establish a voice connection with another mobile station.
- Answer to a connection request: answers a connection request, rejecting or accepting the connection.
- Data channel request: requests a dedicated channel to establish a data connection with another mobile station.
- Registration request: requests the mobile station registration in the system. Typically used after synchronization with the base station is achieved.

Regardless of the type of burst, a *hash-key* is transmitted, which is the mobile station identification in the system.

2.2.5 Dedicated Channel (DCH)

The DCH is a dedicated channel used to carry user or control information between the network and a mobile station.

2.3 System Control

The software is based on a state machine that coordinates the operation of two mobile stations and one base station. The state machine simulates a practical parallel and concurrent operation, and directs information through the appropriate channels. Flexibility allows easy expansion of the system to incorporate more stations, if necessary.

The time unit for state changes is the transmission of one frame or one burst, and consistency with the UTRA specifications regarding all necessary codes and modulation schemes was maintained.

When the program is executed, the system waits for the user to choose the appropriate action. He can set up and turn on the mobile stations. The user can choose either step-by-step or automatic operation.

A typical sequence of operations, with their corresponding states, is described next.

- **System Initialization.** The base station is initialized automatically, while the mobile station initialization occurs only if the user clicks the *On* button. The base station continually monitors RACH and continually sends Synchronization and Broadcast channels.
- **Synchronization.** Before transmission, the synchronization channel frame is randomly cyclic shifted. This allows the simulation of slot and frame synchronization procedures.

If the synchronization for one mobile cannot be achieved, the system keeps trying for that mobile station until it achieves synchronization or the user turns off the mobile station. Meanwhile, the other mobile station can successfully achieve synchronization. The actions for each mobile station happen independently.

- **Detection of the BCH.** This state is necessary as this channel transports general information. It is read several times during simulation because, in a real environment, some information may change.
- **Registration Request.** This notification is used to confirm that the mobile station is synchronized and that it correctly reads all information contained in the BCH. If the mobile station cannot detect the registration confirmation after five frames, it sends another random access burst. If there is no answer after five tries, probably a false synchronization was acquired, forcing the repetition of the whole synchronization process.
- **Registration Confirm.** The base station receives the burst and checks if that mobile station is allowed to register. If registration is granted, the base station sends a downlink response to the mobile, transported in the FACH. The confirmation indi-

cates that the base station detected the Random Access Burst sent by the mobile station.

- **Read Paging Channel and Waiting User Action.** After synchronization and registration, the mobile is fully operational, meaning that it is capable of establishing or receiving a connection request. In this state, the mobile keeps reading the PCH for a connection request, while waits for the user to click the *Connect* button. In this case, the mobile station sends a Random Access Burst requesting a connection. If the addressed mobile station is registered, the base station will send the appropriate connection request to the addressed mobile station.
- **Answer to a Connection Request.** The connection request is verified in the PCH with the use of a hash-key. If the hash-key contained in the paging channel matches the one for the mobile station in its paging group, there is a connection request. Then, the mobile station answers with a Random Access Burst.
- **Wait for Answer to a Connection Request.** At this state, both mobile stations wait for an answer. The requesting station must wait for the base station to send the paging to and receive the answer from the addressed mobile station.
- **Communication Established.** After confirmation of connection for both mobiles, they stay in this state for data exchanging. Once the connection is established the user can send one data file from one mobile station to the other and check if the results are correct. Connection is terminated by the user.

3 Capabilities and Special Features

3.1 Propagation Channels

The modulated signal is filtered by a time-varying multipath channel model that can be either generated internally, according to the parameters specified by the user, or with channel coefficients loaded from a file, allowing the user to perform simulations with recorded strips of actual wideband channel measurements.

Two Gaussian noise sources with zero mean, one in-phase and other quadrature, are low-pass filtered, producing a Rayleigh faded envelope for the channel[2].

At time instant k , $r_{I,k}$ and $r_{Q,k}$ represent amplitudes of the in-phase and quadrature components of the fading signal. The components are Gaussian-distributed random variables such that

$$(r_{I,k+1}, r_{Q,k+1}) = \psi(r_{I,k}, r_{Q,k}) + (1 - \psi)(v_{1,k}, v_{2,k})$$

where $v_{1,k}$ and $v_{2,k}$ are independent Gaussian-distributed random variables with zero mean. The envelope $\sqrt{r_{I,k}^2 + r_{Q,k}^2}$ is Rayleigh distributed.

3.2 Interference

Even though the user has control only over two mobile stations, several other interferers can be included in the transmissions. The interferers carry modulated spread random data which are useful to measure the receiver performance.

3.3 I/O Capabilities

The program has no built-in vocoder. Data to be transmitted may be generated randomly or loaded from a file. This means that any type of data may be transmitted by the simulator, but the user must keep in mind that the system was designed to achieve the required bit-error rates for voice transmission only.

Status report is provided at the status window at the bottom of the main screen, colored indicators, and the *Report* window. The program can also save the following information to files:

- Transmission report: a file with detailed information about all performed transmissions.
- Transmitted data: two files, with the data sent by each mobile station.
- Received data: two files, with the data received by each mobile station.

4 Conclusions

A comprehensive simulation tool which implements all UTRA RTT proposal requirements has been built. It allows tests for different setups through different propagation channels of user-provided signals. All transport channels specified by the UTRA RTT proposal were implemented, and the user is granted choice of spreading factor and codes, compliant to the specifications. The program is flexible to allow introduction of extra modules in the receiver (e.g., adaptive equalizer) or more challenging propagation channels. If used as a teaching-aid tool, the program report and status windows provide complete description of all steps from power-on to data transmission. If used as a research simulation tool, the program allows easy modification to test algorithms for specific tasks and provides detailed reports on the performance of the system.

References

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